

Research Article

Empowering Visually Impaired Students to Explore Mathematical Tactile Graphics Using AI: MathTalk

Siti Suhaila Burihan¹, Raja Noor Farah Azura Raja Ma'amor Shah^{2,*}, Raja Lailatul Zuraida Raja Ma'amor Shah³, Muhammad Ikmal Hakim Shamsul Bahrin⁴, and Hazlina Md Yusof⁵

¹ Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris; sitisuhaila1989@gmail.com

² Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris; raja_farah@fsmt.upsi.edu.my

³ Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris; lailatul.zuraida@fsmt.upsi.edu.my

⁴ International Islamic University Malaysia; muhammad.ikmalhakim@gmail.com

⁵ International Islamic University Malaysia; myhazlina@iium.edu.my

* Correspondence: raja_farah@fsmt.upsi.edu.my; 0195586200

Abstract: Blind students frequently encounter significant challenges when attempting to explore mathematical tactile graphics, especially those involving special complexity, overlapping elements, and abstract concepts. Traditional tactile materials are static and non-interactive, requiring students to rely heavily on teachers or peers, which makes it harder for them to learn on their own and truly understand the concepts. MathTalk, an AI-powered voicebot designed to provide real-time, step-by-step audio instructions that scaffold students through tactile STEM graphics. Developed using the Design and Development Research (DDR) model, MathTalk has three key phases: needs analysis through qualitative interviews with blind students in Malaysia, expert validation using the Fuzzy Delphi Method involving specialist in special education and AI and experimental evaluation with 19 secondary school blind students. Results indicate that a significant majority of students demonstrated improved in understanding, quicker tactile exploration, and increased autonomy in the exploration. The system operates via a simple 8-key tactile interface by using mini keyboard, ensuring ease of use without requiring visual interfaces. Beyond its pedagogical value, MathTalk is scalable, cost effective, and aligned with national education policies that empower inclusive and technology-driven learning environments. Its commercialization potential is strong, with applications in schools and NGOs that support visual impaired communities. MathTalk initiates transformative leaps in accessible STEM education, offering blind students and an equitable and empowering learning tool.

Keywords: assistive technology; tactile graphics; AI; visual impaired; voicebot; STEM

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1. INTRODUCTION

Visual materials are widely used to explain abstract and complex ideas in STEM education, especially in subjects like mathematics and science. For blind students, technology graphics are essential in making this visual information accessible by turning image into touchable diagrams. The tactile graphics help them to understand shapes, positions, and structures, for example, geometric transformations or the anatomy of the human heart (Thévin et al., 2019; Bahrin et al., 2023; Melfi et al., 2020).

However, tactile graphics do not always deliver the same information as visual graphics. The challenges are information overload, difficulty in identifying shapes, and needing to remember multiple details without visual support. It is hard for them to imagine the full picture or follow a complex STEM concept. As a result, they often need help from others, which limits their independence and learning process (Yang et al., 2020; Shoaib et al., 2023; Chase et al., 2020; Gong et al., 2020; Bahrin et al., 2023).

Multimodal technologies such as interactive tactile graphics are crucial for enhancing their learning experience because blind students depend heavily on their sense of hearing and touch (Mikulowski & Brzostek-Pawlowska, 2020). However, teachers often raise concerns over the lack of suitable teaching materials for blind learners, especially for STEM-related visuals such as graphs and diagrams, and they seek tools that can ease these challenges (Ahmed, 2020; Çakmak, 2022).

Emerging technologies in Artificial Intelligence (AI) for guiding tactile graphic exploration will help them. Voice-enabled systems that guide blind users through step-by-step exploration may transform the way tactile content is explored by them. This paper presents MathTalk, a Bahasa Melayu AI voicebot specifically designed to empower blind learners to independently explore transformation graphics through structured audio cues. The innovation was developed through a structured research design, validated by experts, and evaluated through direct classroom implementation.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study adopted the Design and Development Research (DDR) model, comprising three main phases:

Phase 1: Needs Analysis - A qualitative interview was conducted with a group of blind students to identify key issues faced when interpreting tactile STEM graphics. Results indicated high dependency on teachers and significant difficulty in identifying shapes and spatial relationships in the tactile graphics.

Phase 2: Expert Validation - Seven experts in special education, STEM, AI, and Braille were engaged through the Fuzzy Delphi Method to validate the system design, pedagogical features, and usability of MathTalk.

Phase 3: Experimental Study - A pilot study was conducted with three blind students, followed by a main experimental session involving 19 students from a special education secondary school. Each participant interacted with three tactile diagrams of varying difficulty (easy, moderate, hard) using the MathTalk system. Student feedback was collected through individual interviews following their interaction with the MathTalk system.

Figure 1 shows the MathTalk device and its main physical features. MathTalk operates through a mini USB keyboard with only eight tactile-labeled keys. The user interface is minimal and intuitive, allowing students to initiate the voicebot, adjust audio speed, repeat instructions, and toggle modes with ease. The device measures approximately 8.2 inches by 4.4 inches by 3.2 inches, making it compact and portable for classroom or personal use. Key hardware features include a built-in speaker, 3.5mm audio jack for earphone connectivity, built-in microphone, mini USB keyboard, HDMI output, USB hub, and Type-C port for power supply. MathTalk is powered via a Type-C cable and includes a built-in rechargeable power bank, allowing the device to operate without needing to be plugged into a wall outlet. This increases its flexibility and mobility, enabling students to use it in various learning environments such as classrooms, libraries, or at home.

Figure 2 shows the interaction flow of the MathTalk system. The process begins when the student presses the “Talk” button and verbally states the volume and page number. The audio is then converted into text, which is sent to Dialogflow. Dialogflow processes the input and returns the appropriate output texts, which are then converted into audio and played back to the student.

Figure 1. MathTalk Design

Figure 2. MathTalk Flowchart

3. FINDINGS

Findings indicate that MathTalk significantly improved independent engagement with tactile graphics. Quantitative feedback from 19 participants revealed the following: Detailed Likert-scale responses showed that 84.2% agreed they could explore tactile graphics more easily using voice command (see Figure 3), and 94.7% agreed that it made the learning experience faster (see Figure 4). Additionally, 73.7% of respondents agreed that the use of MathTalk was a more effective method for exploring tactile STEM graphics (see figure 5). Furthermore, 63.2% agreed that MathTalk made the exploration of STEM graphics more enjoyable (see Figure 6). Moreover, 89.5% of blinds students agree that MathTalk was an extremely valuable learning tool for exploring tactile graphics, as indicated in Figure 7. Lastly 94.7% of the students agreed or strongly agreed that MathTalk is an essential device for exploring tactile graphics independently, with 68.4% strongly agreed (see Figure 8).

Qualitative feedback also highlighted the appreciation of blind students for the point-by-point navigation in tactile graphics, user-friendly with 8-key keyboard, and clear Bahasa Melayu voice commands. Teachers also reported decreased dependency and improved confidence among students when performing tactile exploration.

Figure 3. Easier with Voice Commands

Figure 4. Faster Learning Process

Figure 5. Effective Exploration Method

Figure 6. More Enjoyable Experience

Figure 7. Helpful Learning Tool

Figure 8. Essential Learning Tool

4. DISCUSSION

Findings show that voice-supported scaffolding can assist in addressing a significant gap in access to visual STEM content for students who are blind. The high level of student agreement, especially when concerning increase ease, engagement, and autonomy, implies that MathTalk not only makes access easier but also simplifies learning. Combining tactile interaction with voice prompts produces a multimodal support system that caters to the sensory capabilities of blind learners.

Through minimizing cognitive overload and enabling self-paced discovery, MathTalk aligns to the principles of Universal Designed for Learning (UDL). It further aids national efforts to integrate AI in special education and promote inclusive, technology-enhanced pedagogy.

With its accessible design, low cost, and screen-free functionality, MathTalk is especially suitable for special education schools. Its classroom readiness ensures that it can be implemented immediately to support blind students in learning more autonomously and effectively.

5. CONCLUSION

MathTalk highlights how AI-powered assistive technology can make a real difference in special education. Its development was guided by thoughtful design, expert input, and classroom testing. All of which showed that it helps blind students learn more independently, stay engaged, and better understand STEM content. With continued refinement and strong policy support, MathTalk has great potential to expand access to STEM education in Malaysia and other countries.

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